

The effect of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S crystalline phase on their solar photoactivation processes

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Abstract

A series of reduced graphene oxide/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S (RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S) nanocomposites (0 < x < 1) with different ratios of Zn/Cd were synthesized via facile hydrothermal route under the optimized experimental conditions and were carefully characterized by various techniques. Because very little is known about the morphology, specific surface area, and crystal phase effects of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S crystals on their photoresponsivity, field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), BET surface area analysis and X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were studied to investigate their effects on photoactivity. Based on the results, crystal phase transition from cubic phase in RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S to hexagonal wurtzite phase in RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S nanocomposites is occurred and the crystalline phase is the main factor influencing the photoresponsivity of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites in photodegradation and photoelectrochemical (PEC) processes under visible light irradiation. According to the results, RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S nanocomposite with hexagonal crystal phase revealed better photocatalytic activity ($k=9.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) and PEC response ($\sim 2.0 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$) in comparison with cubic crystal phase.

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1. Introduction

As an ideal green technology, semiconductor photocatalysts have been attracted continuous interest for their potential applications in environmental cleaning and solar energy utilization. Numerous attempts have been made on the preparation of $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ ($0 < x < 1$) composites to shift the absorption edge of ZnS and to overcome the photocorrosion reaction of CdS. These ZnCdS-based composites have been proved to be an efficient visible-light driven photocatalysts and photoelectrochemical (PEC) photoanodes and have been designed to achieve an enhanced photocatalytic activity as well as hydrogen generation. The photocorrosion resistance, proper band structure, high photocatalytic function and the chemical stability of $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ cause these nanocomposites to be attractive photocatalysts and PEC photoanodes.

Mainly two classes of factors are reviewed affecting the photocatalytic activity of photocatalysts; the electronic factors including band gap energy, photoexcitation, bulk diffusion and surface transfer of carriers; and the morphological factors including the surface area and crystal/particle size. The photocatalytic reactions occur at the interface between catalyst surfaces and the adsorbed organic pollutants. Interestingly, the crystalline phase determines the crystal structure, electronic structure and surface atomic geometry and thus will affect the photoinduced processes. The morphology, crystalline phase and crystal-facet-controlled fabrication of semiconductor materials have recently attracted considerable attention due to the fact that the photoelectric and photocatalytic properties of semiconducting materials can be enhanced by tailoring the surface atomic structures.

Many studies in the investigation of morphology and structure effects on the photocatalytic activity are limited to TiO_2 , TiO_2 -ZnO hybrid, Ag_3PO_4 , CdS, $BiVO_4$, and alkaline niobates.

The main aim of this work is the investigation of the effect of these factors on the photoresponsivity of RGO/ $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ nanocomposites. The synthesized nanocomposites were characterized by various techniques including DRS to obtain the band gap energy, BET surface area analysis to determine the specific surface area and porosity, XPS to measure the chemical state of the elements in the material and XRD to investigate the crystal phases and crystalline sizes of RGO/ $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ nanocomposites. Finally, their visible light responsive PC and PEC activities and role of their particular crystalline phase on photoresponsivity were investigated.

2. Experimental and Methods

Preparation of Graphene Oxide and RGO/ $Zn_xCd_{1-x}S$ Nanocomposites

Graphene oxide (GRO) was prepared by a modified Hummers' method. A facile hydrothermal method was used to prepare RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites by using the precursors of Zn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, Cd(NO₃)₂·4H₂O, thiourea and synthesized graphene oxide. Different molar ratios of Zn/Cd (x= 0, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8, 0.9, 1) were applied in the preparation of nanocomposites by using of various amounts of Zn²⁺ (0.20 M), Cd²⁺ (0.20 M) and CS(NH₂)₂ (1.0 M) precursors. Graphene oxide (0.04 g) was added to solution with continuous stirring and sonication. Subsequently, this mixture was transferred into a 100 mL Teflon-lined autoclave and maintained at 180°C for 24 h. Finally, the obtained product was filtered and washed by DI water for several times and dried at room temperature.

Photoelectrochemical Measurements

At first, to fabricate a photoanode as the working electrode, the electrophoretic method was applied to deposit synthesized graphene oxide (GRO) nanosheets on a titanium (Ti) sheet (1.0×3.0 cm²) as a suitable substrate. During the electrophoretic deposition in solution containing GRO (1.0 mg mL⁻¹) and MgSO₄ (10 mg L⁻¹), GRO is deposited on Ti sheet and reduced to RGO. The photoelectrochemical (PEC) measurements were carried out using a galvanostat/potentiostat Autolab PGSTAT101 instrument and a 400 mW cm⁻² Xe lamp with UV cut-off filter (λ_{off}<400 nm) as the source of visible light irradiation. During all PEC measurements, 0.1 M Na₂S was used as electrolyte.

3. Results and Discussion

Morphology and surface area analysis. The surface morphology of the RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites was investigated by FE-SEM. **Fig. 1** displays the FE-SEM micrographs for RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S with various x values. As it is clear, Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanospheres were hydrothermally deposited on the graphene nanosheets with the particle diameter of about 20 nm. Analysis of all FE-SEM images showed that by changing the Zn/Cd ratio, the morphology of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S was not changed considerably, i.e., these composites are deposited as sponge-like nanospheres. However, the gradual change in morphology occurs by Cd variation and the nanoparticles become smaller by increase in Cd content. On one hand, graphene supplies a platform for Zn_xCd_{1-x}S clusters to nucleate and grow as sponge-like nanospheres, and on the other hand, the adsorption tendency of GRO surface for Cd²⁺ cations is almost the same or slightly higher than that of Zn²⁺. So, higher Cd²⁺ concentration in solution results the higher amounts of loaded Cd²⁺ cations on GRO, and finally, occurring higher nucleation process against the growth of the nuclei.

Fig. 1**Table 1.** Physical properties of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites

Photocatalyst	Crystalline phase	Crystallite size (nm)	Specific surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Pore Size (nm)
RGO/Zn _{0.9} Cd _{0.1} S	Cubic	20.4	40.70±1.50	9.183
RGO/Zn _{0.8} Cd _{0.2} S	Hexagonal	24.3	13.50±1.10	12.542
RGO/Zn _{0.5} Cd _{0.5} S	Hexagonal	40.5	8.02±0.70	19.188
RGO/Zn _{0.2} Cd _{0.8} S	Hexagonal	45.1	7.62±0.80	21.052

The BET (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller) surface areas (S_{BET}) and porous structures of the synthesized samples were investigated by nitrogen adsorption-desorption measurements. Adsorption equilibriums were displayed by isotherm curves regularly. **Fig. 2a** indicates the nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites. These isotherms for all the samples are of type IV with H₃ hysteresis loops indicating the formation of mesopores (2-50 nm) and the presence of uniform slit-like pores in samples. Isotherms of these nanocomposites show high adsorption at a high relative pressure (P/P_0) ranging from 0.8 to 1.0. The Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) pore-size distribution curves (**Fig. 2b**) further confirm that all the prepared materials are mainly consist of mesopores in the wide range from 2 to 50 nm. The specific surface area of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites increases with increase in Zn content probably due to decrease in sample density.^{Error! Bookmark not defined.} According to the obtained results, RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S nanocomposite exhibits the largest specific surface area (40.70 m²g⁻¹) compared with other nanocomposites (Table 1).

Fig. 2

To obtain the elemental composition of synthesized nanocomposites, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) measurements were performed demonstrating the existence of Zn, Cd, C, and S elements in the as-prepared nanocomposites (Fig. S1, Supporting Information).

XRD patterns.

Fig. 3a shows the XRD patterns of various RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites. The characteristic diffraction peaks for RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S were observed at 2θ values of 30.7911°, 33.1577°, 51.3253°, 56.213°, 61.1225° and 66.9832°, attributed to (002), (101), (110), (103), (112) and (202) crystal planes respectively, and the pattern was indexed to the hexagonal RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S (JCPDS 49-1302) as the same as hexagonal wurtzite CdS phase. In XRD pattern of RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S, the peaks at the diffraction angles (2θ) of 31.0226°, 33.2909°, 51.7435°, 55.7091°, 60.6214° and 66.3526° correspond to the (002), (101), (110), (103), (200) and (004) planes respectively, showing hexagonal wurtzite RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S structure (JCPDS 40-0834).

Fig. 3

For RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S sample, however, XRD pattern shows three main diffraction peaks at 2θ of 33.3068°, 55.7712° and 66.199° assigning to (111), (220) and (311) crystal planes of cubic sphalerite Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S nanostructure (JCPDS 24-1137), respectively. Interestingly, these results show that the crystalline phase of the samples transfers from hexagonal wurtzite to cubic phase in RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S when the Zn content increases from x= 0.8 to 0.9. This is in good agreement with the results reported earlier^{Error! Bookmark not defined.} and the results reveal that by changing the Zn/Cd ratio, the structure phase transition occurs and the crystal phase of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples can be controlled through adjusting the Zn/Cd ratio.

The diffraction peaks of samples gradually shift to larger angles with increase in Zn content. The angle related to main peak increases from 30.7911 in RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S to 33.3068 in RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S nanocomposite, indicating the incorporation of Zn²⁺ into the CdS lattice. The crystalline lattice distance (d-spacing) of CdS is decreased due to smaller radius of Zn²⁺ ion (0.74 Å) in comparison with Cd²⁺ (0.97 Å). The d-spacing values for RGO/Zn_{0.2}Cd_{0.8}S, RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S, RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S and RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S were obtained to be 3.3845, 3.3712, 3.3472 and 3.1235 Å, respectively.

The peak shifts indicate that the synthesized samples are not a simple mixture of ZnS-CdS compounds and the nanocomposites of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S are formed. The average crystal sizes of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples were calculated by Scherrer equation and obtained to be 45.1, 40.5, 24.3 and 20.4 nm for x=0.2, 0.5, 0.8 and 0.9, respectively (Table 1). Data shows that upon increasing Zn²⁺ content in RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples, the mean grain size of composite decreases, mainly due to the smaller radius of Zn²⁺ in comparison with Cd²⁺.

Fig. 3

Spectroscopic characterization

The surface composition of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S (x=0.8) nanocomposite was characterized by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) technique. **Fig. 4a** shows a survey XPS spectrum of the RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S sample confirming the existence of Zn, Cd, S, C and O elements which was in agreement with EDS analysis.

The presence of C and O in the survey spectra is due to graphene and the adsorbed water molecules on the surface of nanocomposite, respectively. **Fig. 4b** displays the narrow scan XPS in Zn 2p range for RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S sample. Because of the spin-orbit coupling, Zn 2p is divided to Zn 2p_{3/2} and Zn 2p_{1/2} that are located at bonding energies of 1023 eV and 1046 eV, respectively. Data fitting was done on Zn 2p_{3/2} peak due to the higher intensity of this peak as compared with Zn 2p_{1/2}. **Zn 2p_{3/2} peak contains three separate peaks i.e. A, B and C that are related to Zn-S bond (1022.80 eV), Zn-OH bond (1023.90 eV) and metallic Zn (1020.50 eV), respectively.** As shown in **Fig. 4b**, the major peak is for Zn-S bond (67.6%) which confirms the formation of Zn-S. The XPS spectra of Cd 3d was plotted in **Fig. 4c** including two different peaks. The binding energy of Cd 3d_{5/2} and Cd 3d_{3/2} for Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S sample appeared at 405.40 eV and 412.00 eV, respectively. **Cd 3d_{5/2}, as the most intense peak was separated into two peaks, A and B, which can be ascribed to the Cd-S bond (405.00 eV) and Cd-OH bond (405.80 eV).** Similar to Zn 2p, Cd 3d_{5/2} major peak is located at bonding energy of 405.00 eV, which is assigned to Cd-S bond (77.7%) revealing the formation of CdS in the nanostructure. The positions of S 2p_{1/2} and S 2p_{3/2} high resolution XPS signals for RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S sample that are shown in **Fig. 4d (A and B)** are at the binding energies of 161.10 and 162.30 eV, respectively. It indicates that sulphur exists in the form of S²⁻. The position of oxygen peak was observed at 531.47 eV, which corresponds to OH groups accumulated on the surface of sample which is attributed to the formation of Zn and Cd hydroxides as reported before. By measuring the surface surrounded under XPS peak of each element, surface concentration of Zn, S, O and Cd have been estimated and listed in **Table 2**.

Fig. 4

To calculate the electronic states and the band gap energy (E_g) of the samples, diffuse reflectance spectra (DRS) of the samples were investigated. E_g of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples were calculated by a plot of $(\alpha hv)^2$ vs. photon energy (hv) based on the Kubelka-Munk function ($\alpha hv = A(hv - E_g)^n$). The calculated E_g are depicted in **Table 3**. As it is clear, E_g of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples gradually

increases from 2.50 eV to 3.11 eV by the increase in Zn content. So, the band gap energy of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites can be controlled by changing the molar ratio of Zn/Cd in precursors during the hydrothermal synthesis.

Photocatalytic activity of the RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites

To investigate the effects of various parameters including morphology, specific surface area, pore size diameter, energy band gap (E_g) and the crystal phase of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites on their photoactivity, the photodegradation of methylene blue (MB) as a model compound under the visible light irradiation was studied. The kinetics of the degradation reaction can be described by pseudo first-order equation, $\ln(C_0/C) = kt$.

The C_0/C vs. t and $\ln(C_0/C)$ vs. t plots were presented in Fig. 5. Among RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples, the photoactivity of RGO/CdS and RGO/ZnS samples were also investigated. RGO/CdS sample exhibited the highest photodegradation reaction rate constant ($k=1.09 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$), mainly due to its suitable band gap energy (E_g of 2.4 eV) and high charge carrier (e^- and h^+) mobility (340 and $50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for e^- and h^+ , respectively) compared to a lot of photoactive semiconducting materials. But, because of the photocorrosion and fast recombination of generated charge carriers, CdS is not considered as a suitable photocatalyst. For RGO/ZnS, however, the k value was low ($k=6.6 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) due to its broad E_g and low photoactivity in visible region.

k value were 9.4×10^{-3} , 8.4×10^{-3} , 7.9×10^{-3} and $7.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$, for RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S, RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S, RGO/Zn_{0.2}Cd_{0.8}S and RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S, respectively. From these results, it is clear that the photocatalytic activity of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S is altered by varying the Cd/Zn ratio as reported previously. As Fig. 5 shows, when Cd content decreases, the photodegradation efficiency of MB for RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S becomes higher ($x=0.2, 0.5$) and reaches the highest for $x=0.8$. These results could be attributed to the variation in conduction band (CB) edge position to the moderate and proper position, Error! Bookmark not defined. increase in specific surface area and pore size (**Table 1**).

Fig. 5

Variation in k values (min^{-1}) is as follows:

RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S (9.4×10^{-3}) > RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S (8.4×10^{-3}) > RGO/Zn_{0.2}Cd_{0.8}S (7.9×10^{-3}) > RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S (7.5×10^{-3}).

From these data, the efficient photoactive sample is RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S.

The surface characteristics of the samples such as specific surface area and pore size are not the main parameters affecting the photoactivity of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples. The specific surface area of RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S with higher photocatalytic activity is about 3 times lower than that of RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S. Concerning only the specific surface area, RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S (with higher S_{BET}) should exhibit higher photodegradation reaction rate than other synthesized RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples. Nanocomposites with higher surface area are beneficial for higher charge carrier generation as they have more active sites upon light harvesting, and as a result, more reactions sites. But we have observed an opposite situation. Although the specific surface area of the RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S is the highest, its photoactivity is the lowest. Therefore, specific surface area is not the only decisive factor influencing the photo-activity of the samples. The pore size and crystal size of the samples show a similar trend from $x=0.2$ to $x=0.9$ (Table 1) and decrease by increase in x . The effect of particle size and specific surface area of the photocatalyst on the photodegradation rate (k) has been extensively studied (see for example Ref.) and shown that the increase in surface area increases k . Finally, although the band gap energy of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S increases by increase in x from 0 to 1 (Table 3), the difference between E_g or absorption edge of RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S and RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S is not so high to affect the photoresponsivity of the sample considerably. So, from these findings, it seems that these parameters are not the main factors affecting the photoactivity of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples. Among these various factors, the crystalline phase is seems to be a major factor in the improvement of photocatalytic performance of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites. RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposite with hexagonal crystal phase revealed better photocatalytic activity in comparison with cubic crystal phase.

Graphene improves the charge separation in RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S. As discussed in growth mechanism (Section 3.1.1), Zn²⁺ and Cd²⁺ cations tend to adsorb on the surface of GRO through electrostatic attractions and Zn_xCd_{1-x}S clusters would be nucleate and grow on graphene, and graphene would be as a conductive substrate for Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanoparticles. So, there is an intimate interfacial contact between RGO and Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanoparticles and such a good interfacial contact for RGO - Zn_xCd_{1-x}S, favours the charge carrier transfer process. So, under the illumination, the photogenerated electrons in CB of Zn_xCd_{1-x}S can be easily transferred to RGO, leading to the electron-hole separation. Consequently, graphene improves the charge separation and PC activity.

Photoelectrochemical activity of the RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S

To investigate the photosensitivity of the prepared samples, the photocurrent density was measured in both dark and visible light illuminating conditions as a function of the applied potential of 0.5 V as bias (**Fig. 6a**).

RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S nanocomposites has higher photoresponsivity in comparison with other RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites. From the results (**Fig. 6a**), PEC photocurrent density of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S is altered by varying the Cd/Zn ratio. As Cd content decreases, the photocurrent density of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S becomes higher (x=0.2, 0.5) and reaches the highest for x=0.8. However, further decrease in Cd content, leads to a fast deterioration of PEC photocurrent for x=0.9. As discussed for PC activity, these results indicated that the crystalline phase is the most important factor responsible for PC activity of RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites in comparison with band gap, CB edge position and specific surface area.

Fig. 6

Linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) was also used to investigate the photoresponsivity of Ti/RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S photoanode as a function of applied voltages from -0.2 to 1.2 V in dark and different illumination intensities (**Fig. 6b**). For both electrodes, upon the illumination of the photoanode surface, rapid generation of charge carriers is occurred. The generated photocurrent density of Ti/RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S is much higher than that of Ti/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S mainly due to the effective enhancement in the photogenerated electron lifetime, efficient separation of the photogenerated electron-hole pairs and suppression in charge recombination rate in graphene based nanocomposites.

4. Conclusions

RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S nanocomposites with different molar ratios of Zn/Cd (x= 0, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8, 0.9, 1) were synthesized via a facile hydrothermal method in 180°C for 24 h and were characterized by various techniques including FE-SEM, EDS, BET, XPS, DRS, FT-IR and XRD. BET analysis confirmed the higher specific surface area for RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S while its PC and PEC photosensitivity was lower than that of other synthesized RGO/Zn_xCd_{1-x}S samples. According to the XRD analysis, crystalline phase transition occurs from cubic phase in RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S to hexagonal wurtzite phase in RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S, and their photoactivity studies (including photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical) revealed that the photoresponsivity of the nanocomposites with hexagonal phase is higher than that of cubic phase.

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Fig. 1

FE-SEM images of: (a) RGO/Zn_{0.2}Cd_{0.8}S (b) RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S, (c) RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S, (d) RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S

Fig. 2

BET (a) and BJH (b) of RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S, RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S and RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S. (b): BJH pore-size distribution curves of RGO/Zn_{0.9}Cd_{0.1}S, RGO/Zn_{0.8}Cd_{0.2}S and RGO/Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S

Fig. 3.

XRD patterns of RGO/ZnCdS

Fig. 4

XPS spectra of RGO/ZnCdS

Fig. 5

Photodegradation curves for Methyleneblue by RGO/ZnCdS

Fig. 6

Photoresponse of RGO/ZnCdS

Table 1

Photocatalyst	Crystalline phase	Crystallite size (nm)	Specific surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	Pore Size (nm)
RGO/Zn _{0.9} Cd _{0.1} S	Cubic	20.4	40.70±1.50	9.183
RGO/Zn _{0.8} Cd _{0.2} S	Hexagonal	24.3	13.50±1.10	12.542
RGO/Zn _{0.5} Cd _{0.5} S	Hexagonal	40.5	8.02±0.70	19.188
RGO/Zn _{0.2} Cd _{0.8} S	Hexagonal	45.1	7.62±0.80	21.052

Table 2

Composition	O	Zn	Cd	S	Zn _(ZnS)	Zn _{(Zn(OH)₂)}	Cd _(CdS)	Cd _{(Cd(OH)₂)}
Surface concentration (%)	30.7	46.8	4.1	18.4	67.6	23.1	77.7	22.3

Table 3

Photocatalyst	Absorption edge wavelength (nm)	Band gap energy (eV)
RGO/ZnS	340	3.66
RGO/Zn _{0.9} Cd _{0.1} S	400	3.11
RGO/Zn _{0.8} Cd _{0.2} S	440	2.84
RGO/Zn _{0.5} Cd _{0.5} S	470	2.65
RGO/Zn _{0.2} Cd _{0.8} S	490	2.50
RGO/CdS	530	2.34